

A Theory of Informational Wellbeing

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Introduction

In this paper, I will define a theory of ‘informational wellbeing’ that can help one to identify and measure how various informational practices and policies impact personal wellbeing. By wellbeing I essentially mean “what is non-instrumentally or ultimately good for a person.”¹ First, in Section 1, I will introduce one way of talking about wellbeing—the capability approach to wellbeing. This approach defines wellbeing in terms of one’s “ability to do valuable acts or reach valuable states of being”² (e.g. the ability to go to school, be vaccinated, etc.). I will then outline one theory of wellbeing which uses the capability approach—Martha Nussbaum’s list of Central Human Functional Capabilities. Nussbaum’s list is comprised of ten fundamental capabilities, such as the ability to live a normal lifespan and the ability to be healthy.

In Section 2, I will then demonstrate that certain ‘informational capabilities’ are central to one’s ability to achieve the capabilities on Nussbaum’s list, and thus are central to achieving a high degree of wellbeing according to at least one influential account of wellbeing. The informational capabilities I will focus on are:

- 1) the ability to control access to one’s personal information
- 2) the ability to use one’s personal information
- 3) the ability to ensure the accuracy of one’s personal information
- 4) the ability to live in an environment with adequate network robustness and resiliency

In Section 3, I will then define a theory of informational wellbeing, which describes the relationship between informational capabilities and overall wellbeing. This theory is primarily intended to guide social scientists and policymakers as they seek to measure the impacts of digital technologies and technology policies on wellbeing.

While this is the first attempt to use the capabilities approach to create a theory of informational wellbeing, the capabilities approach has been selectively applied to the use of ICTs in the past. Nicholas Garnham has explored the application of the capabilities approach to communications,³ Shirin Madon has outlined a capabilities approach to

evaluating e-governance reforms in India,⁴ and Björn-Sören Gigler suggested using ‘informational capabilities’ to measure the impact of ICTs in the development context.⁵ In each case, the capabilities approach was determined to be a better approach for assessing the impact of ICTs on people’s lives compared to metrics like the establishment of infrastructure.⁶

1 The Capability Approach to Wellbeing

The capability, or capabilities, approach developed by Amartya Sen is a theoretical framework for describing wellbeing in terms of one’s ability to achieve combinations of ‘valuable functionings,’⁷ or states of being and doing. Examples of valuable functionings include being vaccinated, living in a warm house, or going to school. A *capability*, meanwhile, is one’s ability to achieve various combinations of valuable functionings. An example from Nussbaum’s list of capabilities, which I will describe presently, is the ability to enjoy recreational activities.⁸ This capability could be measured by assessing one’s ability to enjoy various activities such as games, art, theatre, reading, watching TV, etc. This may, in turn, include assessments of whether one has free time, the necessary financial resources, people to play with, and knowledge of games. By focusing on one’s ability to achieve various combinations of functionings rather than on specific functionings, the capabilities approach places a high value on freedom. For example, those using the capabilities approach care if one has the ability to engage in recreational activities, not whether one plays checkers or chess or, for that matter, any game at all.

The capability approach is not a complete theory of wellbeing in and of itself. As Serena Olsaretti says, “[The capability approach] only identifies a space for individual and social evaluation, a standard of advantage, which can then be used for descriptive purposes.”⁹ As a way of talking about wellbeing, it is flexible enough to work with a number of different conceptions of what it means to live a good life. While I will focus on one conception in this chapter—Nussbaum’s list of Central Human Functional Capabilities—one could easily use another list of capabilities in its stead.

For my purpose, two types of capabilities are important: ‘fundamental capabilities’ and ‘informational capabilities.’ By fundamental capabilities I mean the capabilities which enable a person to pursue a “minimally flourishing life”¹⁰ (e.g. the ability to be healthy, the ability to live a normal lifespan), while an ‘informational capability’ is one’s ability to achieve various valuable informational functionings. An example of an informational capability is the ‘ability to control who has access to one’s personal information,’ while valuable informational functionings which comprise this capability may include living in a country with data regulations that require positive consent for the use of one’s information, understanding how one’s personal information is used, using strong passwords, and using communication tools with end-to-end encryption. The value of specific informational capabilities and functionings will be dependent on the local context. For example, having strong passwords is not a valuable functioning if one does not have personal access to ICTs that require passwords.

1.1 Nussbaum’s List of Central Human Functional Capabilities

While Sen does not specify the list of relevant capabilities for wellbeing, one such influential list is Nussbaum’s Central Human Functional Capabilities. This list is Nussbaum’s attempt to identify the capabilities which are required for a life to be “not so impoverished that it is not worthy of the dignity of a human being.”¹¹ The list is not intended to be a comprehensive account of all that is good for a person, but a list of capabilities that states should provide to ensure individuals have the ability to pursue a “minimally flourishing life.”¹² I will use Nussbaum’s list as an example of a set of ‘fundamental capabilities,’ with the understanding that future research may reveal additional fundamental capabilities or suggest alterations to the list below.¹³ Below I will quote at length from Nussbaum’s *Women and Human Development: The Capabilities Approach*, although I have cut down the descriptions of each capability as appropriate. The ten capabilities on Nussbaum’s list include:

- 1) **Life.** Being able to live to the end of a human life of normal length...
- 2) **Bodily Health.** Being able to have good health...
- 3) **Bodily Integrity.** Being able to move freely from place to place; having one’s bodily boundaries treated as sovereign...
- 4) **Senses, Imagination, and Thought.** Being able to use the senses, to imagine, think, and reason – and to do these things in a “truly human” way, a way informed and cultivated by an adequate education...Being able to use imagination and thought in connection with

experiencing and producing self-expressive works ... Being able to use one’s mind in ways protected by guarantees of freedom of expression with respect to both political and artistic speech, and freedom of religious exercise. Being able to search for the ultimate meaning of life in one’s own way. Being able to have pleasurable experiences, and to avoid non-necessary pain.

- 5) **Emotions.** Being able to have attachments to things and people ...
- 6) **Practical Reason.** Being able to form a conception of the good and to engage in critical reflection about the planning of one’s life...
- 7) **Affiliation.**
 - A. Being able to live with and toward others... to have the capability for both justice and friendship...
 - B. Having the social bases of self-respect and non-humiliation; being able to be treated as a dignified being whose worth is equal to that of others. This entails, at a minimum, protections against discrimination on the basis of race, sex, sexual orientation, religion, caste, ethnicity, or national origin....
- 8) **Other Species.** Being able to live... in relation to... the world of nature.
- 9) **Play.** Being able to laugh, to play, to enjoy recreational activities.
- 10) **Control over One’s Environment.**
 - A. Political. Being able to participate effectively in political choices that govern one’s life...
 - B. Material. Being able to hold property (both land and movable goods), not just formally but in terms of real opportunity;...having the right to seek employment on an equal basis with others; having the freedom from unwarranted search and seizure.¹⁴

Nussbaum compiled this list after years of cross-cultural discussion, making it the product of a kind of Rawlsian ‘overlapping consensus.’¹⁵ As Nussbaum acknowledges, some of these goods (e.g. health) are ‘natural goods.’ Whether or not one acquires these natural goods is partly due to luck. For these goods, the role of the state is to try to provide the social basis for the good (e.g. access to healthcare, clean water) rather than the good itself (e.g. health).¹⁶

While acknowledging that this list is not without controversy,¹⁷ I will use it to demonstrate that informational capabilities are central to at least one influential account of wellbeing. Furthermore, it is worth stating that even if one subscribes to a very different ultimate account of wellbeing, one may still be able to accept that the capabilities on Nussbaum’s list are useful for some policy purposes. For example,

one may think that wellbeing is ultimately about satisfying one's preferences, but nonetheless accept that the ability to access healthcare furthers that goal.

2 The Importance of 'Informational Capabilities' to Nussbaum's List

While none of Nussbaum's capabilities explicitly reference digital technologies, in this section I will argue that certain informational capabilities are often central to one's ability to achieve the fundamental capabilities described by Nussbaum, and thus one's ability to achieve a high degree of wellbeing within her account. The 'informational capabilities' I will focus on include:

- 1) the ability to control access to one's personal information
- 2) the ability to use one's personal information
- 3) the ability to ensure the accuracy of one's personal information
- 4) the ability to live in an environment with adequate network robustness and resiliency

While there are other valuable informational capabilities, these four are adequate to illustrate the importance of informational capabilities (as a class) to one's ability to achieve the capabilities on Nussbaum's list.

In the following subsections, I will present examples which illustrate the importance of each informational capability. For instance, I will look at India's Aadhaar program as an example of having the ability to use one's personal information. While exploring each example, I will highlight the relevant intersections with Nussbaum's list by **bolding** the relevant fundamental capability. These examples should be treated as being illustrative of the importance of the given informational capability and not as a comprehensive treatment of the topic.

2.1 The Ability to Control Access to Personal Information

While there are many examples of the importance of *being able to control access to one's personal information*, here I will focus on the inability to control access to personal photos. First, I will explore the example of the actress Jennifer Lawrence, who had a series of nude photos stolen in 2014, and then I will widen the discussion to revenge pornography more generally.

In 2014 hundreds of images of celebrities stored on Apple's iCloud service were stolen and subsequently released online.¹⁸ Many of these images depicted the celebrities in various states of undress. While many celebrities were affected, the actor Jennifer Lawrence was particularly vocal about what the experience was

like. She described how the theft was not merely a property crime, but a violation of her **bodily integrity**. In describing the theft, Lawrence said, "It's taking somebody's intellectual property but also my body. It was violating on a sexual level."¹⁹ As the photos began to appear online, she tried to work on a public statement, but she says, "every single thing that I tried to write made me cry or get angry."²⁰ She described herself as, "Just so afraid." The leak caused her unnecessary emotional pain (**Senses, Imagination Thought**), caused her to lose social bases of self-respect and non-humiliation (**Affiliation**), and plausibly led to employment discrimination (**Control of One's Environment**). Certainly, with more conservative fans, the leaking of the photos harmed Lawrence's reputation—although the scale of this harm is hard to assess. She also acknowledged the important social role of these photos in maintaining her relationship with her partner (**Affiliation**) saying, "I started to write a [public] apology, but I don't have anything to say I'm sorry for. I was in a loving, healthy, great relationship for four years. It was long distance, and either your boyfriend is going to look at porn or he's going to look at you."²¹

While Lawrence has been particularly vocal about her experience, her experience is not uncommon. Mudasir Kamal and William J. Newman describe the mental effects of revenge, or non-consensual, pornography more generally:

The distress includes anger, guilt, paranoia, depression, or even suicide. There may also be deterioration in personal relationships and feelings of isolation. The humiliation, powerlessness, and permanence associated with these... crimes leave victims engaged in a lifelong battle to preserve their integrity. Consequently, victims of revenge pornography suffer from similar enduring mental health effects as described by victims of child pornography, such as depression, withdrawal, low self-esteem, and feelings of worthlessness.²²

In both the Lawrence case and the case of non-consensual pornography more generally, one's ability to control access to one's personal information is central to one's ability to achieve many of the fundamental capabilities listed by Nussbaum.

The capabilities approach is particularly useful for thinking about the Lawrence case because it emphasizes that it is the loss of the *ability* to control who has access to one's photos rather than the taking or sharing of the photos themselves that is the problem. Lawrence not only did not feel shame about taking the photos and sharing them with her boyfriend, but she specifically acknowledged that this activity strengthened their relationship. The capabilities approach values one's freedom by acknowledging that what constitutes a good life is not

the same for everyone. While for some people taking nude photos and sharing them with one's romantic partner is not a valuable functioning, for others it is. A more simplistic objective list approach to wellbeing may fail to account for the positive aspects of this activity.

2.2 The Ability to Use One's Personal Information

The second informational capability I will highlight is *the ability to use one's personal information to achieve a host of secondary goods*. This informational capability is particularly important because bureaucracies have typically used identifying informational artefacts (e.g. IDs, biometrics) as the gateway to everything from securing a home loan, to receiving government benefits, to participating politically. While this informational capability is important in non-digital contexts (e.g. paper passports, drivers licenses, etc.), I will explore a contemporary digital example—Aadhaar, India's biometric ID program.

The Aadhaar program uses citizens' iris scans, fingerprints, and photographs to generate a twelve-digit ID number and an ID card. The aim of the program is for that ID card and one's biometrics to be the mechanism by which one claims welfare, health services, food rations, pension benefits, registers for certain schools, and votes. In theory at least, having the ability to use one's biometric information is central to many Indians' ability to live a normal lifespan (**Life**), be healthy (**Health**), participate politically (**Control of One's Environment**), and receive an adequate education (**Senses, Imagination, Thought**). One example of Aadhaar's promise is the experience of Manisha Kamble, a homeless seventeen-year-old living in Mumbai. Speaking of her experience, Manisha said, "In India, you're nothing without Aadhaar."²³ Without a birth certificate or address, Manisha was essentially invisible to the state. After a charity helped her get a card, she was able to register for a school (**Senses, Imagination, Thought**), and when she turns 18 she will be able to use her card to register to vote (**Control of One's Environment**).²⁴

In practice, the program has often failed to achieve its purpose and has been plagued with technical and logistical problems. While Manisha's experience illustrates the promise of Aadhaar, others have lost previously available resources, such as food rations, due to technical problems with the program, such as unreliable internet (especially in rural regions), faulty fingerprint readers, and insecure databases.²⁵ In other cases, individuals who lack fingerprints through a lifetime of manual labour, age, or amputation can be turned away from food ration offices or other essential services.²⁶ Jean Dreze, an economist studying Aadhaar, has identified at least a dozen individuals who died of hunger in 2018 after either

being unable to enrol in the program or being turned away when their information could not be accessed.²⁷

One instance where the concept of informational capabilities is particularly useful is for assessing the impact of the program's poor cybersecurity. As the technology lawyer Mishi Choudhary says, "any compromise of such a database is essentially irreversible for a whole human lifetime: no one can change their genetic data or fingerprints in response to a leak."²⁸ Unfortunately, the system has already been hacked. One investigative journalist was able to buy access to a billion people's information for a mere seven dollars.²⁹ While this seems problematic, it is not always easy to point to immediate financial or reputational harm resulting from such breaches. As a result, one may (and courts often do) conclude that no harm has actually occurred from data breaches.³⁰ However, using the language of capabilities one can argue that one's wellbeing has been affected by these breaches as one has lost the ability to control access to one's personal information and the ability to use one's biometric information in the future. These impacts are realized the moment the database is compromised regardless of whether or not one's identity is ever actually stolen.

2.3 The Ability to Ensure the Accuracy of Personal Information

The third informational capability I will highlight is *the ability to ensure the accuracy of one's personal information*. There are numerous examples of the importance of the ability to ensure the accuracy of one's personal information ranging from the accuracy of one's digital medical records (**Health, Life, Bodily Integrity**) to the odd case of Constantin Reliu—a Romanian man who was incorrectly declared dead after having lived abroad for several decades. Despite appearing in court *in person*, he was told that his appeal was too late; he would have to remain officially deceased. Speaking of the impact, Reliu said, "I am officially dead, although I'm alive...I have no income and *because I am listed dead, I can't do anything* [emphasis mine]."³¹ This inaccuracy and Reliu's inability to correct it prevents him from voting (**Political Control Over One's Environment**), accessing health services (**Life, Health**), owning property, and working (**Material Control Over One's Environment**). While Reliu's case may seem like a surreal edge case, less dramatic examples are common, such as individuals having difficulty scrubbing erroneous incidents from their credit history (**Material Control Over One's Environment**) or struggling to recover from identity theft.³²

The more a society uses personal information for, the more important it is to be able to ensure its accuracy. China's new social credit system (SCS) is a case in

point. This mandatory program assigns points based on what the government considers good behaviour and docks points for what the government considers bad behaviour in four areas: government affairs, judicial affairs, social activities, and commercial behaviours.³³ Data sources include, but are not limited to, financial records, tax records, social media, and travel information. This data is collected by disparate sources and then shared and integrated into a centralized system.³⁴ Examples of bad behaviour include bad driving, buying too many video games, and bribing officials.³⁵ People with low scores can be banned from traveling by train and plane, prevented from leaving the country (**Bodily Integrity**), barred from hotels, have their internet speed throttled, lose out on certain types of jobs (**Material Control of One's Environment**), and possibly be publically shamed (**Affiliation**).³⁶ Inaccuracies may occur because of slander, human error, buggy code, or because the data scheme cannot account for the complexities of real life. I will sidestep the question of whether this is a good or bad social program. What is important for my purposes here is that when such a program is in place, it is important that one has the ability to ensure the information being used is accurate.

While one might want to argue that it is simply better for one's information to actually be accurate than to have the *ability* to ensure that it is accurate, there are cases where it might be in one's advantage for one's personal information to be inaccurate. For example, someone who has served time in prison may not want their criminal record to show up on their Facebook page, a shorter individual may not mind that their dating profile adds a few inches to their height, or a human rights worker in China may be better off if the SCS says they were playing video games while they were actually meeting with a pro-democracy activist. This is not to say that it is unproblematic for people to make things up or to say that they should have the ability to deliberately falsify personal information. Rather, it is to say that one's wellbeing depends on having the ability to ensure one's information is accurate, not necessarily on it actually being accurate.

2.4 The Ability to Live in an Environment with Adequate Network Robustness and Resiliency

The final informational capability I will highlight is *the ability to live in an environment with an adequate level of network robustness and resiliency*. This ability is essential to being able to rely on critical infrastructure, such as water treatment plants, emergency services, the banking sector, dams and chemical plants. Additionally, in the digital age, it is critical to the proper functioning of digital voting machines (**Political Control of One's Environment**), hospital infrastructure (**Health, Life**), government systems like Aadhaar, and one's ability

to communicate with friends (**Affiliation**). While this ability is less important in societies which do not rely heavily on digital networks, in regions like North America and Europe the reliance of critical infrastructure and bureaucracy on digital networks means that network robustness and resiliency impacts one's ability to achieve nearly all of Nussbaum's fundamental capabilities.³⁷

These four informational capabilities are merely illustrative of how digital information and its use, control, accessibility, and accuracy can impact one's ability to achieve Nussbaum's fundamental capabilities. Other potentially important informational capabilities include the ability to avoid algorithmic bias, the ability to communicate confidentially, and literacy. In the next section, I will more formally define informational wellbeing and then discuss a number of potential applications.

3 A Theory of Informational Wellbeing

In the last section, I argued that given the ubiquity of digital technologies and their role in 21st century bureaucracies, one's ability to achieve a high degree of wellbeing within Nussbaum's account depends on one's ability to achieve certain informational capabilities. Given this importance, there is value in a concept of 'informational wellbeing' that can act as a shorthand for all of the various ways informational capabilities impact our ability to achieve fundamental capabilities. I will define informational wellbeing as:

An individual has a high degree of informational wellbeing to the extent they have achieved the 'informational capabilities and functionings' (e.g. the ability to control access to their personal information, etc.) which are necessary to achieve fundamental human capabilities (e.g. the ability to live a normal life span, etc.).

This is certainly not the only way one could define a concept of informational wellbeing, but it has a number of features that make it useful for both policymakers and technology producers seeking to promote personal wellbeing.

First, the theory is flexible enough to work in a wide variety of cultural contexts. While I have used Nussbaum's list of fundamental capabilities, one could substitute another list of fundamental capabilities without altering the definition I have presented above. Nussbaum has even acknowledged that each entry on her list can be "more concretely specified in accordance with local beliefs and circumstances."³⁸ The same can be said for informational capabilities and functionings. In some contexts internet access may be central to one's ability to use one's information, while in other contexts having access to a telephone or the postal service may be sufficient. This theory of

informational wellbeing does not assume that just because someone lives in a less technologically advanced society that they necessarily have worse informational wellbeing.

Second, the theory is sufficiently non-technical to be understood by policymakers, politicians, technology producers, and citizens. This makes it easier for social scientists to tailor the theory to local contexts and for local stakeholders to participate in the process of specifying valuable capabilities and functionings. This is not to say that technical measures (e.g. encryption strength, bandwidth) should be avoided when measuring one's ability to achieve certain functionings. In some cases, technical assessments may be the best way to measure a given informational capability.

Third, the theory is measurable. Measurability is important for policymakers and technology producers. Without being able to quantify impacts to one's wellbeing, it is difficult to determine proportional responses and to set appropriate funding levels. Furthermore, my theory of informational wellbeing can likely be measured using data available to civilians. Examples include data related to technological literacy, access to and usage of the internet, what technological services people use, and network reliability. If my theory relied upon non-publicly accessible data, its utility as a policy tool would decrease as it would be challenging to verify that assessments of informational wellbeing were defensible and accurate.

Fourth, my theory takes into account the *perception gap*. By the perception gap I mean that we generally cannot sense changes to the state of our personal information. If one breaks one's arm, one can immediately perceive that one's physical wellbeing has decreased. Similarly, the concept of mental wellbeing is largely based on the quality of one's immediately perceptible mental experience. By contrast, one could have one's identity stolen, but only realize the harm when applying for a loan, checking one's bank account, or attempting to log into an online account that has been compromised. The 'perception gap' suggests that objective list approaches, like the capability approach, are better suited to measuring informational wellbeing than approaches which rely on one reporting one's affect or satisfaction, such as the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS).

One might want to object to the notion that one's wellbeing can be affected despite one not perceiving the change.³⁹ While this might be true for assessing the experiential quality of one's life,⁴⁰ informational wellbeing is not intended to describe this aspect of wellbeing. Rather it is a standard of advantage—a way to make comparison's between people to guide political action.⁴¹ In this context, objective measures are appropriate. These four features are not necessary

conditions for a theory of informational wellbeing—a theory would not have to be flexible or measurable or non-technical to count as a plausible account of informational wellbeing. However, they are positive features which increase the approach's utility.

4 Utility

Using this theory of informational wellbeing, one can systematically think through how a given policy, intervention, or product may impact one's ability to achieve fundamental capabilities and, by extension, a high degree of personal wellbeing. This kind of assessment could be carried out by either assessing how a technology policy or product directly affects fundamental capabilities (i.e. how a policy impacts one's ability to be healthy, live a normal lifespan, etc.) or by assessing how a technology policy or product affects those informational capabilities which are necessary to achieve fundamental capabilities (i.e. how a policy impacts one's ability to control access to one's personal information). These assessments can then in turn be used to design policies and products which improve personal wellbeing.

How precisely these assessments would be performed will be the subject of future research, however, there are useful examples in the capabilities literature. Two of these include Jonathan Wolff and Avner de-Shalit's version of the "York Model," which uses both objective and subjective assessments to measure each relevant functioning,⁴² and Sen's work with Mahbub ul Haq creating the Human Development Index (HDI). The first is a more detailed assessment of advantage, while the second is a very high-level index that measures three metrics intended to be indicative of one's general capability—life expectancy, years of schooling, and per capita gross national income.⁴³ Operationalizing the theory of informational wellbeing will require specifying the fundamental capabilities which constitute overall wellbeing, identifying the informational capabilities that enable one to achieve those fundamental capabilities, determining appropriate measures for these informational and fundamental capabilities, and the collection of data.

Conclusion

The theory of informational wellbeing defined in this paper provides one way of assessing technology policies and products in wellbeing terms. Such assessments are valuable for understanding the impact of technology policies and products on individuals' lives, especially compared to alternative metrics such as kilometres of infrastructure established and expenditure. While the theory defined in this paper is not the only way one could define 'informational wellbeing,' it is measureable, non-

technical, able to be modified for local contexts, and grounded in an influential account of personal wellbeing.

¹ Roger Crisp, "Well-Being," *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, Sep. 6, 2017, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/well-being> (accessed 30 May 2018).

² Amartya Sen, "Capability and Wellbeing," in *The Quality of Life*, eds. Martha Nussbaum and Amartya Sen (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1993), 30.

³ Nicholas Garnham, "Amartya Sen's 'Capabilities' Approach to the Evaluation of Welfare: Its Application To Communications," in *Beyond Competition: Broadening the Scope of Telecommunication Policy*, eds. Bare Cammaerts and Jean-Claude Burgelman (Brussels: VUB University Press, 2000), 25-36.

⁴ Shirin Madon, "Evaluating The Developmental Impact Of E-Governance Initiatives: An Exploratory Framework," *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries* 20, no. 5 (2004): 1-13.

⁵ Björn-Sören Gigler, "'Informational Capabilities' - The Missing Link for the Impact of ICT on Development," *The World Bank*, working paper series no. 1, (March 2011), <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/227571468182366091/pdf/882360NWP0Box30series0no10March2011.pdf> (accessed Oct. 24, 2018).

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Amartya Sen, "Capability and Wellbeing."

⁸ Nussbaum, *Women and Human Development: The Capability Approach* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000), 78-79.

⁹ Serena Olsaretti, "Endorsement and Freedom in Amartya Sen's Capability Approach," *Economics & Philosophy* 21, no. 1 (2005): 91.

¹⁰ Martha Nussbaum, *Creating Capabilities* (Cambridge, MA: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2011), 33.

¹¹ Nussbaum, *Women and Human Development: The Capability Approach*, 72.

¹² Martha Nussbaum, *Creating Capabilities*, 32-33.

¹³ Jonathan Wolff and Avner de-Shalit, *Disadvantage* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007), 9.

¹⁴ Nussbaum, *Women and Human Development: The Capability Approach*, 78-80. Note that Nussbaum tends to speak about her list as an account of justice rather than wellbeing per se. This is because it is focused on what states have a duty to provide their citizens and not an attempt to list all that is good for a person. Ultimately we are both discussing what is often called advantage. As the lines blend between wellbeing and advantage, I believe it is appropriate to use Nussbaum's list to discuss wellbeing, while recognizing that she might disagree with this use.

¹⁵ John Rawls, *A Theory of Justice*, Revised Ed., (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1971, 1999), 340.

¹⁶ Nussbaum, *Women and Human Development: The Capability Approach*, 81-82.

¹⁷ Richard Arneson, "Perfectionism and Politics," *Ethics* 111 (2000): 37-63.

¹⁸ Charles Arthur, "Naked Celebrity Hack: Security Experts Focus on iCloud Backup Theory," *The Guardian*, Sep. 1, 2014, <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2014/sep/01/naked-celebrity-hack-icloud-backup-jennifer-lawrence> (accessed Jan. 24, 2019).

¹⁹ Oprah Winfrey, "The Jennifer Lawrence Interview, by Oprah Winfrey," *The Hollywood Reporter*, Dec. 6, 2017, <https://www.hollywoodreporter.com/features/jennifer-lawrence-interview-by-oprah-winfrey-1064576> (accessed April 18, 2018).

²⁰ Sam Kashner, "Both Huntress and Prey," *Vanity Fair*, November 2014, <https://www.vanityfair.com/hollywood/2014/10/jennifer-lawrence-photo-hacking-privacy>.

²¹ Ibid.

²² Mudasir Kamal and William J. Newman, "Revenge Pornography: Mental Health Implications and Related Legislation," *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law Online* 44, no. 3 (2016): 359-367.

²³ Lauren Frayer, "India's Biometric ID System Has Led To Starvation For Some Poor, Advocates Say," *NPR*, Oct. 1, 2018, <https://www.npr.org/2018/10/01/652513097/indias-biometric-id-system-has-led-to-starvation-for-some-poor-advocates-say?t=1538831766242>.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Indrani Basu, "AADHAAR: Fading Fingerprints Mean This Ageing Space Scientist Can't Care For His Son," *Huffington Post*, April 19, 2018, https://www.huffingtonpost.in/2018/04/19/an-81-year-old-space-scientist-wants-the-supreme-court-to-save-senior-citizens-from-aadhaar_a_23414358 (accessed April 6, 2019).

²⁷ Frayer, "India's Biometric ID System Has Led To Starvation For Some Poor, Advocates Say."

²⁸ Mishri Choudhary, "Viewpoint: The Pitfalls Of India's Biometric ID Scheme," *BBC News*, April 23, 2018, <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-asia-india-43619944>.

²⁹ Frayer, "India's Biometric ID System Has Led To Starvation For Some Poor, Advocates Say."

³⁰ Daniel Solove, "'I've Got Nothing to Hide' and Other Misunderstandings of Privacy," *San Diego Law Review* 44 (2007): 768.

³¹ Shaun Walker, "Romanian Court Tells Man He Is Not Alive," *The Guardian*, March 16, 2018, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2018/mar/16/romanian-court-tells-man-he-is-not-alive>.

³² Charlene Jennett, Sacha Brostoff, Miguel Malheiros, and M. Angela Sasse, “Adding Insult To Injury: Consumer Experiences Of Being Denied Credit,” *International Journal of Consumer Studies* 36 (2012): 549-555. doi:10.1111/j.1470-6431.2012.01120.x.

³³ Fan Liang, Vishnupriya Das, Nadiya Kostyuk, Muzammil M. Hussain, “Constructing a Data-Driven Society: China's Social Credit System as a State Surveillance Infrastructure,” *Policy & Internet* 10, no 4 (2018): 415-453.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Mara Hvistendahl, “Inside China’s Vast New Experiment in Social Ranking,” *Wired*, Dec. 14, 2017, <https://www.wired.com/story/age-of-social-credit/> (accessed April 24, 2018).

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ It is worth noting that this is a capability—like the ability to live in a malaria-free environment—where it is unclear that it is the capability that matters as much as achieving a specific functioning. Would anyone be better off living in a malarial zone or in an environment with poor cyberhealth? This question is also a feature of some of the capabilities on Nussbaum’s list, such as health. For further discussion on this matter see: Olsaretti, Serena. “Endorsement and Freedom in Amartya Sen's Capability Approach.”

³⁸ Martha Nussbaum, *Women and Human Development: The Capabilities Approach*, 77.

³⁹ For a summary of various objective and subjective accounts of wellbeing see Derek Parfit, *Reasons and Persons* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006), Appendix I.

⁴⁰ T.M. Scanlon, *What We Owe to Each Other*, (Cambridge, MA: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 1998), 112.

⁴¹ Wolff and de-Shalit, *Disadvantage*.

⁴² Ibid., 110-118.

⁴³ United Nations Development Programme, “Human Development Index (HDI),” United Nations Development Programme: Human Development Reports, <http://hdr.undp.org/en/content/human-development-index-hdi> (accessed 12 October 2018).